

1 **Environmental and social determinants of anuran lekking behavior:**

2 **intraspecific variation in populations at thermal extremes**

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19 **Abstract**

20 Environmental and social factors are critical to determine the timing and duration of
21 lekking behavior since they provide species with signs to maximize benefits over costs in
22 sexual displays. However, these factors have rarely been studied under different
23 environmental conditions, and thus it remains unclear whether exogenous factors affecting
24 group displays show a general pattern within-species or whether they are population-
25 specific. Using *audio-trapping* techniques, we compared factors influencing the daily
26 *occurrence* and *duration* of lekking behavior in two populations of *Hyla molleri* and two
27 populations of *H. meridionalis* located at the thermal extremes (coldest vs. hottest) of their
28 Iberian distribution range. From 12,240 hourly recordings over one season, AIC
29 multimodel inference revealed that the major determinants of *chorus occurrence* were
30 similar between populations and species (i.e., *chorus size* the previous day, and daytime
31 air temperature, relative humidity and barometric pressure), and accounted for 51–79% of
32 its variance. In contrast, the major determinants of *chorus duration* differed between
33 populations and species (i.e., *chorus size*, number of day, and air temperature and relative
34 humidity at the onset of the chorus), and accounted for 38–69% of its variance. Our
35 findings suggest that the decision making related to lek attendance is environment-
36 dependent, takes place at time between lekking events and is associated with exogenous
37 factors that may be both stable across species ranges and population-specific when
38 populations are under different climatic conditions. This intraspecific variation might be
39 underlain by plasticity mechanisms providing tree frogs with means to cope with changing
40 environments. Moreover, social facilitation related male-male acoustic competition seems
41 to play a relevant role on the daily time invested by males in lek attendance.

42 **Keywords:** Calling activity · Lek · Climatic response · Social facilitation · *Hyla* · Audio-
43 trapping

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44 Introduction

45 Lek mating systems have been described in a wide range of animals, such as mammals,
46 birds, amphibians, fish, and insects (e.g., Lloyd 1867; Downes 1969; Wells 1977; Clutton-
47 Brock et al. 1993; Höglund and Alatalo 1995). Males breeding in leks or choruses
48 congregate synchronously on reproductive sites to defend non-resource-based territories
49 from competitors and to attract mating partners by advertisement signals (Bradbury 1981;
50 Höglund and Alatalo 1995). Attendance to group displays is crucial for individual fitness
51 in lekking species, although there is often variation in mating success of males within a
52 lek (Widemo and Owens 1995; Mackenzie et al. 1995; Kokko et al. 1998). However,
53 lekking behavior is also highly costly in terms of energy (Taigen and Wells 1985;
54 Prestwich 1994; Schwartz et al. 1995; Grafe and Thein 2001) and predation risk (Ryan et
55 al. 1981; Tuttle and Ryan 1981), and thus it is expected that selective pressures favor
56 mechanisms in lekking species to determine the optimal time for lek formation (Murphy
57 1999; Brooke et al. 2000; Murphy 2003).

58 The timing and duration of group displays are influenced by environmental or
59 social factors, or both, that have been found to act as determinants of the temporal patterns
60 of lekking and chorusing behavior in multiple organisms (e.g., Schneider 1971; Pemberton
61 and Balmford 1987; Han and Gatehouse 1991; Baines 1996; Brooke et al. 2000; Berg et
62 al. 2006). Temperature, light intensity and relative humidity (or rainfall) are the most
63 common environmental factors associated with the onset and maintenance of anuran
64 chorusing (Blair 1961; Heinzmann 1970; Schneider 1971; Obert 1975; Fukuyama and
65 Kusano 1992; Henzi et al. 1995; Navas 1996; Oseen and Wassersug 2002; Steelman and
66 Dorcas 2010), although other weather variables may play a role in chorus formation,
67 including barometric pressure, wind speed or lunar cycle (Blankenhorn 1972; Henzi et al.
68 1995; Cree 1989; Oseen and Wassersug 2002; Murphy 2003; Grant et al. 2009; Steelman

69 and Dorcas 2010). Moreover, calling activity from conspecifics can elicit acoustic displays
70 at different scales and levels (e.g., Capranica 1966; Ryan and Rand 1998; Brooke et al.
71 2000), and thus social facilitation also affects strongly on the timing and duration of group
72 acoustic displays (Wells and Taigen 1986).

73 Interspecific comparisons, both in sympatry and allopatry, have suggested that the
74 set of exogenous determinants of lek or chorus formation tend to be species-specific
75 (Blankenhorn 1972; Obert 1975; Salvador and Carrascal 1990; Oseen and Wassersug
76 2002; Berg et al. 2006; Steelman and Dorcas 2010). Additionally, prolonged breeders
77 seem to respond to more exogenous factors than explosive breeders and be affected by
78 different factors throughout the breeding season (Wells 1977; Oseen and Wassersug
79 2002), but some exceptions have also been found (Blankenhorn 1972; Salvador and
80 Carrascal 1990).

81 In contrast with the abundant literature about between-species variation, little
82 attention has been addressed to investigate the within-species variation in the responses to
83 exogenous factors mediating lek attendance. Studies measuring the effects of
84 environmental variables on chorusing activity have mostly been conducted at single
85 locations, where one or more species respond to the same climatic conditions (Blair 1961;
86 Heinzmann 1970; Schneider 1971; Blankenhorn 1972; Obert 1975; Salvador and
87 Carrascal 1990; Fukuyama and Kusano 1992; Henzi et al. 1995; Moreira and Barreto
88 1997; Hatano et al. 2002; Oseen and Wassersug 2002; Steelman and Dorcas 2010).
89 Therefore, it remains unclear whether such variables and their effects may be extrapolated
90 onto populations across the distribution of the species and hence under different
91 environmental or social conditions. The few intraspecific studies available were not
92 specially focused on studying the effect of clearly divergent climate regimes, since they

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93 compared populations at small spatial scales (Ritke et al. 1992; Navas 1996; Brooke et al.
94 2000).

95 The comprehension of factors affecting the timing and duration of these sexual
96 displays under different environments provides insight into a remaining open question:
97 whether the exogenous factors determining lek formation show a general pattern within-
98 species or whether they are population-specific. Since exogenous factors eliciting lekking
99 behavior must reflect optimal local conditions for lek formation (e.g., Höglund and
100 Alatalo 1995; Brooke et al. 2000), it may be expected that species respond to different
101 exogenous factors when they inhabit in different environmental or social contexts. Such
102 response would imply the occurrence of mechanisms of local adaptation or phenotypic
103 plasticity providing lekking species with means to confront changing environments. Thus,
104 the study of intraspecific variation of exogenous determinants of group displays may
105 contribute to reveal the occurrence of such mechanisms and helps in understanding of how
106 species cope with environmental heterogeneity, which is a grand and urgent task for
107 current biology (Schwenk, 2009). To our knowledge, this is the first study that examines
108 the intraspecific variation of environmental and social determinants of anuran lekking
109 behavior (chorus occurrence and duration).

110 The technical difficulty to monitor simultaneously distant populations has been so far
111 one of the reasons of the lack of intraspecific long-term acoustic surveys. As used in this
112 study, the recently developed automated recording systems (Peterson and Dorcas 1994;
113 Frommolt et al. 2008; Obrist et al. 2010) now facilitates the simultaneous monitoring of
114 calling activity over complete seasons and in multiple populations, even if the populations
115 are located at the latitudinal margins of the species' distribution range. Moreover, this
116 sampling method prevents changes to the behavior of the study species owing to observer
117 presence as well as enables subsequent thorough analyses of the recordings with enhanced

118 detection and reduced observer bias (Bridges and Dorcas 2000; Oseen and Wassersug
119 2002; Acevedo and Villanueva-Rivera 2006; Steelman and Dorcas 2010; Llusia et al.
120 2011).

121 Here, we examine the environmental and social factors that determine lek formation in
122 two species of Palearctic tree frogs, *Hyla molleri* and *H. meridionalis*. With automated
123 recording systems (ARS), chorusing activity and weather conditions were monitored in
124 four populations (two per species) located at the thermal extremes (coldest vs. hottest) of
125 their Iberian distribution range and exposed to different climatic conditions. Thereby, we
126 attempt to test whether exogenous determinants of lekking behavior show a general
127 pattern within-species or whether they are population-specific. Specifically, we address
128 the following two questions: i) what environmental and social factors are associated with
129 the daily occurrence and duration of tree frog chorus? ii) Do these factors differ across
130 populations (*hot* vs. *cold*), species (*H. molleri* vs. *H. meridionalis*) and indexes of chorus
131 formation (*occurrence* vs. *duration*)? Furthermore, we discuss the implications of our
132 findings for predictions on the effects of current climate change on anuran populations.

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134 **Material and Methods**

135 Species and study sites

136 Iberian tree frog (*Hyla molleri* Bedriaga, 1890) and Mediterranean tree frog (*H.*
137 *meridionalis* Boettger, 1874) share numerous morphological, behavioral, and ecological
138 traits. They are both prolonged breeders and aquatic egg-layers that aggregate in choruses
139 around ponds, streams or other water bodies from early spring to summer during their
140 breeding season (García-París et al. 2004). Within this period, males are typically hidden
141 in bushes or underground hideouts at daytime, and before sunset they migrate to breeding

142 points, where they vocalize while floating on water or perched on emergent vegetation
143 (Paillette 1967; Schneider 1974; Márquez and Tejedo 1990; Márquez et al. 2005). Lek-
144 like mating system has been described in these species (Friedl and Klump 2005; Jaquiéry
145 et al. 2009), therefore they are suitable models to study the mechanisms underlying
146 lekking behavior, as recent studies have showed with some closely related hylids (e.g.,
147 *Hyla arborea*) and other lek-breeding anurans (Grafe 1997; Friedl and Klump 2005;
148 Broquet et al. 2009; Knopp et al. 2008; Castellano et al. 2009; Jaquiéry et al. 2009).
149 Sympatric populations of the study species occur in central and western Iberia, where
150 hybridization takes place occasionally (Oliveira et al. 1991; Barbadillo and Lapena 2003).

151 The study was conducted on populations located at the thermal extremes of the Iberian
152 distribution range of tree frogs: two localities of *Hyla molleri* (cold and hot, hereafter
153 *CHmo* and *HHmo*) and two localities of *H. meridionalis* (cold and hot, hereafter *CHme*
154 and *HHme*; Fig. 1). *CHmo* occurs above the timberline of the mountain area of the
155 Somiedo Natural Park in northern Iberia (1490 m.a.s.l., Asturias, Spain), in a small
156 temporary pond (25 x 18 m) surrounded by bushes (*Genista florida*), alpine prairies, and
157 grasslands. The area is under an oceanic climate, with cool and wet summers (*Cfb*,
158 Köppen-Geiger climate classification; Peel et al. 2007). *HHmo* and *CHme* populations are
159 sympatric in west-central Iberia and breed in a medium-sized permanent pond (62 x 53 m)
160 located at 408 m.a.s.l. within an agricultural land of the São Mamede Natural Park
161 (Portalegre, Portugal). In this site, climate shows transitional features between oceanic and
162 Mediterranean climates, with warm and dry summers (*Csb*; Peel et al. 2007). *HHme* is
163 located in the coastal marshes of the Doñana Biological Station in southern Iberia (3
164 m.a.s.l., Huelva, Spain), in a large-sized temporary pond (160 x 101 m) with sedges
165 (*Scirpus spp.*) and halophytic vegetation, where it undergoes a typical Mediterranean

166 climate, with hot and dry summers (*Csa*; Peel et al. 2007). Geographic coordinates,
167 meteorological conditions and other features of the study sites are listed in Table 1.

168 To quantify how thermally extreme were the climate regime of each study site, we
169 compared the annual mean temperature of the 10x10 km UTM square including the study
170 site (Universal Transverse Mercator coordinate system; Hijmans et al. 2005) with that of
171 the remaining 10x10 km UTM squares of the Iberian distribution range of the study
172 species (1257 squares for *H. molleri* and 1074 squares for *H. meridionalis*; Pleguezuelos
173 et al. 2002; Loureiro et al. 2008). In the Iberian Peninsula, between 73% and 99% of the
174 UTM squares of the species ranges had a higher annual mean temperature than that of the
175 UTM square in the cold study sites (7.6 °C in *CHmo*; 15.4 °C in *CHme*; Table 1).
176 Conversely, between 78% and 97% of the UTM squares had a lower annual mean
177 temperature than that of the UTM square in the hot study sites (15.4 °C in *HHmo*; 17.9 °C
178 in *HHme*; Table 1). The hot-cold pairs of sites show a similar thermal difference,
179 approximately 5 °C, measured as mean temperature of the wettest quarter (4.3 °C vs. 9.2
180 °C, for *H. molleri* pair; 9.2 °C vs. 14.3 °C, for *H. meridionalis* pair; Table 1).

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182 Data collection

183 Anuran acoustic displays and weather conditions were monitored during an entire
184 breeding season (from December 2006 to July 2007; Table 2) with *audio-trapping*
185 techniques (i.e., acoustic automated recording systems, ARS) and data loggers. Sound
186 monitoring was extended 10–12 weeks before and after the expected period of calling
187 activity for each population ensuring its complete recording. Weather monitoring was also
188 extended to the previous and the subsequent year to record the meteorological conditions
189 outside the period of reproductive activity. The ARS consisted of an omnidirectional
190 condenser microphone (Fonestar FCM-626) and a solid-state digital recorder (Marantz

191 PMD660, D&M Professional), powered by a 12-V battery and controlled by a custom-
192 built programmable timer (Western Kentucky University; Cambron and Bowker 2006).
193 The equipment was housed in watertight boxes, with an external microphone placed 5–10
194 m from the shore of the ponds and 1–2 m above ground to maximize the probability of
195 detection of anuran vocalizations. Microphones were protected from rainfall and humidity
196 by a plastic shield. During the whole study period, sound recordings (44.1 kHz, 16-bit,
197 MP3 format) were obtained with a schedule of 3 minutes per hour, 24 hours per day,
198 which it has shown to be an adequate sampling regime for the most anuran calling surveys
199 (Shirose et al. 1997; Dorcas et al. 2009). To standardize the ARS-based sound monitoring
200 (recording levels, detection spaces, etc.), we followed the method described in Llusia et al.
201 (2011). Data download and battery replacement were carried out every three or four
202 weeks. During the study period, 12,240 3-min long audio files were collected from 86
203 monitoring days in *CHmo*, 175 in *HHmo* and *CHme*, and 252 in *HHme*. In total, the
204 automated recording equipment was inactive in the field 18 days in *CHmo*, 62 in *HHmo*
205 and *CHme*, and 15 in *CHme* due to different technical problems, thus preventing the
206 inclusion of data from those days. To detect anuran chorusing from either of the two
207 species, we subsequently listened to the recordings in the laboratory, and visually
208 inspected oscillograms and audio-spectrograms (Peak 4.0, BIAS, Inc.; XBAT, Cornell
209 University). Sound recordings were assigned to a *calling index* value between 0 to 5,
210 following a modified version of the NAAMP protocol (i.e., 0 = absence of calling activity;
211 1 = single vocalizations lacking continuity from one or two isolated individuals; 2 =
212 individuals can be counted, space between calls; 3 = calls of individuals can be
213 distinguished, lack of overlapping; 4 = intermittent chorus, calls are discontinuous, some
214 overlapping; 5 = full chorus, calls are constant, continuous, and overlapping; Weir and
215 Mossman 2005).

216 Air and water temperatures ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and relative humidity (%) were measured *in situ*
217 every 5 minutes with data loggers (Pendant 64 Kb and HOBO Pro V2, Onset Computer).
218 The air data loggers were placed 5–10 m from the shore, in the vegetation that surrounds
219 the ponds, 15–35 cm above ground, and with probes protected from rainfall and direct
220 sunlight. The water data loggers were in the water surface at 1–2 m from the shore of
221 breeding ponds. Accuracy in the measurements was 0.3°C for temperatures and 2.8% for
222 humidity. In addition to the data loggers, hourly measurements of barometric pressure
223 (hPa) and cloud cover (okta) were obtained from three automatic weather stations of the
224 Spanish and Portuguese National Meteorological Services, Agencia Estatal de
225 Meteorología (AEMET, Spain) and Instituto de Meteorologia (IP, Portugal). The weather
226 stations are located in Oviedo (335 m.a.s.l., 39 km from *CHmo*), Portalegre (597 m.a.s.l.,
227 11 km from *HHmo* and *CHme*), and Mazagón (41 m.a.s.l.; 28 km from *HHme*). Time and
228 date of the moon phases during 2006 and 2007 were also recorded (Planetary System
229 Laboratory, NASA) because reproductive phenology has been associated with lunar cycle
230 in some anuran species (FitzGerald and Bider 1974; Grant et al. 2009). For each hour of
231 the study period, we assigned an equidistant percentage value that ranged from 0% (at
232 time of new moon) to 100% (at time of full moon) as a measure of the moon phases.

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234 Response and predictor variables

235 From the initial hourly time series of data, two daily response variables were calculated
236 for each study site: the daily occurrence of tree frog chorus (hereafter, *chorus occurrence*)
237 and the nightly chorus duration (hereafter, *chorus duration*). European tree frog males
238 attend choruses mostly between sunset and sunrise (Schneider 1971) and tend to move in
239 and out of the breeding points between chorusing events (Grafe and Meuche 2005). Thus,
240 the temporal patterns of chorusing activity within the breeding season are expected to be

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241 associated with a daily decision making that may be based at least on twofold decision: i)
242 whether to migrate to the breeding ponds to attend a chorus, which determines *chorus*
243 *occurrence* (presence / absence), and ii) when cease to call and leave the chorus, which
244 determines *chorus duration* (number of hours). Moreover, the daily time series were
245 selected instead of the hourly information because hourly time series may suffer from
246 autocorrelation in errors of the explanatory variables, so that they fail the assumption of
247 independent values required for regression methods (Sokal and Rohlf 1995).

248 The response variable *chorus occurrence* was assigned a value of 1 (presence) when
249 any recording within the day (i.e., from sunrise to sunrise) achieved a value of the *calling*
250 *index* between 2 and 5, whereas it was assigned a value of 0 (absence) when all recordings
251 within the day had a value of *calling index* between 0 and 1. Tree frogs may occasionally
252 emit isolated calls from their hideouts under rocks or in bushes at times of the day or even
253 periods of the year that leks are not formed in the water. Thus, the recordings with a
254 *calling index* value of 1 (i.e., single vocalizations lacking continuity from one or two
255 isolated individuals), which corresponds to tentative vocal activity outside of group
256 displays, were included as absence of *chorus occurrence*. The response variable *chorus*
257 *duration* was calculated as the number of recordings within the day (i.e., from sunrise to
258 sunrise) with a value of *calling index* between 2 and 5. In addition to these variables, a
259 multinomial variable was also calculated as the daily maximum value of the *calling index*
260 (hereafter, *chorus size*).

261 The temporal window of the daily time series of *chorus occurrence* was selected so
262 that those series were composed of a similar number of presences and absences, i.e., a
263 balanced design. Since only a low percentage of days within the calling season lacked
264 choruses (mean < 10% of the nights), days before and after the period of calling activity
265 were added in an amount equal to the duration of this period (i.e., half before and half

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266 after). We selected this temporal window to include environmental values to which tree
267 frogs had been subjected just before and after the breeding season (between 3 and 8
268 weeks), and that might have influenced the onset and end of the group displays. Moreover,
269 this balanced design with equal prevalence of presences and absences was used to avoid
270 the statistical problems associated with unequal sample size between treatments in
271 generalized linear models (Hosmer and Lemeshow 1989; Fielding and Bell 1997; Cramer
272 1999; Montgomery 2001; Manel et al. 2001; Gelman 2005). The temporal window of the
273 daily time series of *chorus duration* was composed only of days with presence of chorus.

274 To determine the environmental and social factors influencing *chorus occurrence* and
275 *chorus duration* in each study site, multiple binomial and linear regression analyses were
276 computed, respectively. The set of independent variables entered into the multivariate
277 analyses was composed of 17 variables for binomial regressions and of 16 variables for
278 linear regression (Table 3 and 4). These variables were selected as those that could
279 presumably influence tree frogs or be assessed by tree frogs before the daily beginning of
280 the chorus attendance (in the case of *chorus occurrence*) and before the daily ending of the
281 chorus attendance (in the case of *chorus duration*). To examine potential predictors of
282 *chorus occurrence* (Table 3), we used the daytime means, minima and maxima of the
283 environmental variables monitored, as well as trend values from previous days and values
284 two hours before sunset (when typically choruses are close to be initiated). *Daytime* was
285 considered from sunrise to two hours before sunset, when no chorus occurs in the study
286 sites and it is expected that the decision making related to migration to the breeding points
287 and chorus attendance takes place. To examine potential predictors of *chorus duration*
288 (Table 4), we used the mean values of the environmental variables monitored during the
289 chorus and values at the onset of the chorus. Values at the onset of the chorus were
290 selected instead of values at the end of the chorus because the former were independent of

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291 the number of hours of chorusing activity unlike the latter (e.g., air temperature at the end
292 of the chorus is consistently found to be colder in long choruses than in short ones since
293 air temperature typically decrease along the night, and hence a causal relationship between
294 temperature at the end of the chorus and *chorus duration* would be found as a statistical
295 artifact). Water temperature was added among the explanatory variables of *chorus*
296 *duration* because most of tree frog males in the study sites typically called from the
297 surface of the water. In addition, quadratic terms of temperature variables were included in
298 both binomial and linear regressions to examine the presence of temperature optima.

299 Calling activity may diminish along the reproductive period due to mortality, decline
300 in energy reserves of callers or due to previous mating success in part of the population
301 (e.g., Murphy 1994). Thus, the number of days elapsed since the onset of the study period
302 was added to the regression analyses. Furthermore, the social structure of aggregations
303 (e.g., the number of males within the group displays) in turn may influence the chorus
304 attendance and the time invested by males in the chorus (Wells and Taigen 1986), as a
305 result of male-male sexual competition and evoked vocal responses (e.g., Capranica 1966;
306 Ryan and Rand 1998). Hence, *chorus size* the same night was also entered into regression
307 models as independent variable to investigate whether nightly social conditions might
308 affect *chorus duration*. In addition, to account for lagged effects of social factors in *chorus*
309 *occurrence* and *chorus duration* one lagged predictor variable was included in both
310 binomial and linear regressions (Table 3 and 4). *Chorus size* the previous night is expected
311 to increase the likelihood of *chorus occurrence* as a proxy of the number of males in
312 suitable conditions for sexual displays (hormonal levels, energetic reserves, etc.), so that
313 larger proportion of males attending chorus the previous night would presumably enable
314 to more males maintain chorusing activity in subsequent nights. Moreover, *chorus size*
315 may also increase the communication distance between conspecifics, and thus on the

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316 range of social facilitation of calling activity. Interaction terms were excluded from the
317 regression models because of the large number of candidate predictors.

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319 Statistical analyses

320 Multimodel inference was applied as model selection approach (Burnham and
321 Anderson 2002; Johnson and Omland 2004; Richards et al. 2011; Symonds and Moussalli
322 2011), using Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) corrected for small sample sizes
323 (Akaike's second-order AIC, AICc; Burnham and Anderson 2004). This approach
324 grounded on the K-L information theory is specially suited to test multiple competing
325 hypotheses from complex systems, providing advantages over other methods, such as
326 weighing of candidate models and model averaging (Johnson and Omland 2004). All
327 possible regression models from every combination of the independent variables (i.e., full
328 set of models) were computed and compared each other with AICc and Akaike's weights
329 (w_i). Regression models with $\Delta AICc < 2$ were considered as equally plausible models and
330 retained for model averaging. In model averaging, standardized regression coefficients (β)
331 and relative importance of the predictor variables in the AIC multimodel inference (Σw_i :
332 sum of Akaike weights of the models where each variable was selected) were calculated to
333 enable comparisons of the effect of predictors on the response variable.

334 Regression diagnostics confirmed absence of multicollinearity, autocorrelation,
335 overdispersion and significant departures from normality in all final models.
336 Multicollinearity was assessed with variance inflation factor (VIF; Montgomery and Peck
337 1992). When any VIF value ≥ 3 (Zuur et al. 2010), one of the predictor variables involved
338 in multicollinearity was removed from the set of independent variables and multimodel
339 procedure was restarted from the onset. Univariate regression R^2 as well as standardized
340 regression coefficients (β) and relative importance (Σw_i) of the predictor variables in the

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341 averaged model were used as criteria to select the variables excluded due to
342 multicollinearity. Furthermore, model residuals showed lack of autocorrelation in all cases
343 as tested by Durbin-Watson statistic ($d = 1.93\text{--}2.38$, $P\text{-value} > 0.39$ in all cases). The ratio
344 of residual deviance to degrees of freedom was below 1 in all binomial models, which
345 indicates absence of overdispersion. Normality of the residuals was assessed with Shapiro-
346 Wilk test and graphical methods.

347 Multiple ordered logistic regressions were also attempted with an alternative response
348 variable (i.e., *chorus size*, daily maximum of the *calling index*, with values between 0 and
349 5), but these regression analyses yielded poor goodness of fit in all cases (i.e., explained
350 deviances $< 15\%$ and failures of the normality assumption). Thus, the daily presence of
351 chorus was entered as binomial variable (*chorus occurrence*) instead of *chorus size*, and
352 the ordered logit analysis rejected.

353 Finally, to test whether species respond to the same environmental and social
354 variables across populations at thermal extremes, we followed a standard method to
355 contrast among regression equations (Neter et al. 1996). Two regression models were
356 fitted and statistically compared: i) a combined model for both conspecific populations by
357 joining the data sets from the cold and hot population; and ii) the same previous model,
358 but including a categorical variable for population and an interaction term between this
359 variable and each of the remaining predictors. Combined models showing higher
360 information loss and smaller strength of evidence (i.e., $\Delta\text{AICc} > 2$ and lower Akaike
361 weights) than models with separate equations for populations would point out differences
362 in the regression equations (intercepts, slopes, or both) for the conspecific populations
363 (Neter et al. 1996; Murphy 2003), and hence this would imply environmental and social
364 determinants being population-specific, rather than showing a general pattern within
365 species. This statistical procedure was used to compare between each pair of conspecific

1 366 populations (*CHmo* vs. *HHmo* and *CHme* vs. *HHme*), for both *chorus occurrence* and
2 367 *chorus duration*. Additional comparisons were also conducted between species at the
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4 368 sympatric site (*HHmo* vs. *CHme*) in order to test whether the two tree frog species respond
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7 369 to the same environmental and social variables when they are subjected to the same
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9 370 conditions.

11 371 All statistical analyses and figures were conducted with R 2.15.0 (R Development
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13 372 Core Team 2012).

16 373

19 374 **Results**

22 375 Weather conditions

26 376 In all study sites, temperature conditions during the study period were similar to those
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28 377 during the reference period of 1971–2000 (“typical meteorological year”; AEMET 2008).
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30 378 Annual rainfall was less abundant (20–40% of its range in 1971–2000), except in the
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32 379 southernmost site (*HHme*) where rainfall reached similar rates to those of the 1971–2000
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34 380 period (“typical meteorological year”; AEMET 2008). Within *H. mollerii* sites, weather
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36 381 conditions were markedly warmer and drier in *HHmo* (mean \pm SD; air temperature: 15.0
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38 382 $^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 7.2$; relative humidity: 62% \pm 20) than in *CHmo* (9.2 $^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 6.3$; 95% \pm 13). For *H.*
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40 383 *meridionalis*, the hot site was also warmer, but less dry (*HHme*, mean \pm SD; air
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42 384 temperature: 15.6 $^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5.8$; relative humidity: 74% \pm 18) than the cold site (*CHme*; 13.0
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44 385 $^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5.8$; 66% \pm 18), although these differences in air temperature and relative humidity
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46 386 were less marked than in the pair of *H. mollerii* sites. Rates of other weather factors
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49 387 measured in the study sites are summarized in Table 1.
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58 389 Chorus activity

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390 Tree frog choruses were recorded between 38 and 118 nights per site (Table 2) and their
391 presence was largely continuous across the breeding season. The percentage of nights
392 lacking chorusing activity within the season averaged only 9.8% (range 5–21%). In the
393 majority of the calling nights (> 61%), *chorus size* was assigned to its maximum level (= 5).
394 In contrast, *chorus duration* was markedly more variable than *chorus occurrence* and
395 *chorus size*, with larger coefficients of variation and a duration range of 1–13 hours per
396 calling night (Table 2). In all populations, most of the recordings containing tree frog
397 choruses occurred between sunset and sunrise (> 90%).

398 The duration of chorusing activity, both seasonally (i.e., number of nights from the
399 first to the last night of *chorus occurrence*) and nightly (i.e., number of hours calling per
400 night or *chorus duration*), were strongly population-specific and longer in the hot sites
401 than in the cold sites, as shown in Table 2. In *HHme*, tree frogs formed the most prolonged
402 and larger choruses of the four populations, between 26 December and 21 May and with a
403 mean duration of 7.2 ± 3.2 hours (tracks) per calling night ($n = 118$). In sympatry, under
404 the same environmental conditions, choruses of the two species lasted similarly per night
405 (*HHmo*: 5.6 ± 1.9 hours; *CHme*: 5.1 ± 2.5 hours), but calling season was a month shorter
406 for *H. meridionalis* (*HHmo*: $n = 84$ nights; *CHme*: $n = 56$ nights).

407 408 Predictive models of chorusing activity

409 From the Akaike multimodel inference, 6–14 logistic regression models per population
410 showed $\Delta\text{AICc} < 2$ (App. 1) and accounted for 51–79% (weighted average of the
411 explained deviance for all selected models per population) of the daily likelihood of
412 presence / absence of tree frog chorus (*chorus occurrence*) by including a total of 5–8
413 predictor variables (Table 5; App. 1). In all populations, the predictor variable with the
414 highest strength of evidence ($\Sigma w_i = 1.00$; i.e., included in all models with $\Delta\text{AICc} < 2$) and

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415 the highest magnitude effects ($\beta = 4.54\text{--}22.54$) was prevSizeCHORUS (i.e., the maximum
416 size of the chorus the previous night, a *calling index* with values between 0 and 5) that
417 increased the likelihood of presence of chorusing activity. Moreover, other environmental
418 factors were consistently included in models with $\Delta\text{AICc} < 2$ (e.g., maxDayTEMP,
419 chgTEMP, chgPRESS, dayRH or prevRH, etc.), although with relative importance ($\Sigma w_i =$
420 0.10–1.00) and magnitude effects ($\beta = -0.84\text{--}2.12$) differing among populations (Table 5;
421 Fig. 2; App. 1). In most of the study sites, the likelihood of presence of tree frog chorus
422 increased on warmer and wetter days with a rise in air temperature and barometric
423 pressure from the previous day.

424 Similarly, 2–13 linear regression models per population showed $\Delta\text{AICc} < 2$ (App. 2)
425 and accounted for 38–69% (weighted average of R^2 for all selected models per population)
426 of the variance of the nightly number of hours of chorusing activity of tree frogs (*chorus*
427 *duration*) by including a total of 6–7 predictor variables (Table 6; App. 2). All predictor
428 variables of these models showed standardized regression coefficients (β) below 1, which
429 suggest that major predictors had similar magnitude effects on *chorus duration* in all
430 populations. According to their strength of evidence and magnitude effects, four factors
431 were the most prominent determinants of *chorus duration*: sizeCHORUS ($\Sigma w_i = 0.84\text{--}$
432 1.00; $\beta = 0.30\text{--}0.80$), numDAY ($\Sigma w_i = 0.05\text{--}1.00$; $\beta = -0.63\text{--}0.18$), onsetAirTEMP ($\Sigma w_i =$
433 0.27–1.00; $\beta = 0.16\text{--}0.78$) and onsetRH ($\Sigma w_i = 0.31\text{--}1.00$; $\beta = 0.17\text{--}0.49$), which were
434 incorporated as predictor in 3–4 of the populations. Overall, the number of hours in which
435 tree frog choruses were active increased in nights earlier the breeding season, with larger
436 number of males attending choruses and with warmer and wetter air at the onset of the
437 calling activity (Table 6; Fig. 3). Among populations, the influence of sizeCHORUS on
438 *chorus duration* was positively associated with the population size and the seasonal mean
439 of *chorus duration*. The sized-biggest population showed the largest rates of *chorus*

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440 *duration* as well as the largest magnitude effects of sizeCHORUS in regression models of
441 *chorus duration* (HHme: 7.2 h/night; $\beta = 0.8$), while the sized-smallest population showed
442 the shortest rates in these two indices (CHmo: 3.6 h/night; $\beta = 0.0$). Other predictor
443 variables were nightCLOUD (i.e., mean barometric pressure [hPa] during the chorus) and
444 prevCHORUS (i.e., the number of hours of chorusing activity the previous night), which
445 were both positively associated with *chorus duration* in HHme ($\Sigma w_i = 1.00$). Thus, *chorus*
446 *duration* exhibited similar number of associations with social and environmental factors
447 than *chorus occurrence*, although with less strong effects and accounting for a lower
448 portion of its variance.

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450 Model comparisons

451 The statistical comparisons between regression models revealed that the intercepts and the
452 slope coefficients of the environmental and social determinants of *chorus occurrence* were
453 similar between conspecific populations at thermal extremes, whereas those of *chorus*
454 *duration* differed markedly. Higher information loss was obtained in all the models of
455 *chorus occurrence* including an indicator for population (i.e., models with separate
456 equations for each population; *H. molleri*: $\Delta AICc = 22.2$; *H. meridionalis*: $\Delta AICc = 10.5$;
457 in sympatry: $\Delta AICc = 21.9$) than in the combined models with common equations for both
458 populations, which showed a larger strength of evidence in all cases (*H. molleri*: $w_i = 1.00$;
459 *H. meridionalis*: $w_i = 0.99$; in sympatry: $w_i = 1.00$). In contrast with the determinants of
460 *chorus occurrence*, coefficients for *chorus duration* exhibited marked differences between
461 populations, as shown by higher Akaike weights in all the models with an indicator for
462 population and interaction terms between this factor and each predictor (*H. molleri*: $w_i =$
463 1.00 ; *H. meridionalis*: $w_i = 1.00$; in sympatry: $w_i = 0.99$). The combined models of *chorus*
464 *duration* with common equations for both cold and hot populations resulted in models

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465 with higher AICc values (*H. mollerii*: $\Delta\text{AICc} = 29.2$; *H. meridionalis*: $\Delta\text{AICc} = 24.0$; in
466 sympatry: $\Delta\text{AICc} = 9.8$). From the Akaike multimodel inference in combined models of
467 *chorus duration*, the indicator for population were incorporated in all models with ΔAICc
468 < 2 ($\Sigma w_i = 1.00$ in all cases; *H. mollerii*: $\beta = 1.07$; *H. meridionalis*: $\beta = -0.60$; in sympatry: β
469 $= 0.09$) as well as several interaction terms (*H. mollerii*: numDAY, onsetAirTEMP,
470 meanWatTEMP, and onsetRH; $\Sigma w_i = 0.04\text{--}0.58$; $\beta = -0.80\text{--}0.50$; *H. meridionalis*:
471 onsetRH, onsetAirTEMP, prevCHORUS, numDAY, and sizeCHORUS; $\Sigma w_i = 0.39\text{--}1.00$;
472 $\beta = -0.17\text{--}0.65$; in sympatry: numDAY; $\Sigma w_i = 1.00$; $\beta = -0.38$).

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474 **Discussion**

475 Determinants of *chorus occurrence*

476 Multimodel inference supports the effect of the daytime weather conditions on the daily
477 lek formation in tree frogs (*chorus occurrence*), suggesting that decision making related to
478 chorus attendance (e.g., migration and calling behavior) is environment-dependent and
479 takes place at time between lekking events. As shown in previous works, air temperature
480 (Heinzmann 1970; Schneider 1971; Blankenhorn 1972; Obert 1975; Salvador and
481 Carrascal 1990; Fukuyama and Kusano 1992; Brooke et al. 2000; Oseen and Wassersug
482 2002; Steelman and Dorcas 2010), relative humidity (Oseen and Wassersug 2002;
483 Steelman and Dorcas 2010) and barometric pressure (Blankenhorn 1972; Henzi et al.
484 1995; Brooke et al 2000; Oseen and Wassersug 2002; Steelman and Dorcas 2010)
485 markedly affected the temporal patterns of anuran chorusing activity ($\beta > 1$), although
486 their magnitude effects differed among populations and species. This implies that
487 environmental factors may act as cues for lekking species to determine the optimal time to
488 lek, as suggested by Brooke et al. (2000). The prominent costs associated with lekking

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489 behavior (e.g., Ryan et al. 1981; Tuttle and Ryan 1981; Taigen and Wells 1985; Prestwich
490 1994; Grafe and Thein 2001) would promote that males attending lek or chorus restrict
491 their presence in arenas or breeding points according to environmental conditions.

492 Such behavioral strategy is expected to be specially marked in species with prolonged
493 breeding patterns (Wells 1977; Oseen and Wassersug 2002), as both species of this study,
494 in which the arrival of females at the breeding points occurs asynchronously along the
495 season. Our results were in agreement with the hypothesis proposed by Wells (1977) that
496 predicts that prolonged breeders displaying in lek or chorus would respond intensely to
497 environmental conditions as a means of regulating their energy budget throughout long
498 reproductive periods and of increasing the probability to encounter receptive females.
499 Moreover, Murphy (2003) found a similar response to environmental variables in both
500 females and males of *Hyla gratiosa*, suggesting that males could assess the same variables
501 to predict female abundance and thereby the payoff of attending the chorus, which might
502 explain the widespread correlations between females and males attending leks or choruses
503 (e.g., Henzi et al. 1995; Höglund and Alatalo 1995).

504 Among the daytime environmental variables, those recorded along the entire day (i.e.,
505 mean and maximum) or calculated as changes from previous days (i.e., trends) were
506 selected over variables measuring conditions at a short time before chorus formation (i.e.,
507 two hours before sunset). This indicates that males may be influenced across a large
508 temporal window by weather factors that elicit responses more than two hours before the
509 onset of chorusing activity. In contrast, Blankenhorn (1972) found temperature at 19h as
510 the major predictor factor of chorusing in a German population of *Hyla arborea*.

511 In most populations, maximum or minimum daytime of air temperature was positively
512 associated with *chorus occurrence*, suggesting that warmer daytime favor chorusing
513 activity in populations of tree frogs located at both cold and hot thermal extremes.

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514 Ectothermy conditions multiple physiological and behavior processes in amphibians,
515 including those related to acoustic communication (reviewed in Narins 2001). In other
516 temperate zone anurans, temperature has been found to be the most common weather
517 factor influencing calling activity (e.g., Heinzmann 1970; Fukuyama and Kusano 1992;
518 Oseen and Wassersug 2002; Steelman and Dorcas 2010). Within particular thresholds of
519 temperature, higher body temperatures favor calling activity because they enhance some
520 physiological processes involved in sound production, such as metabolic rate, heart rate,
521 circulating sexual hormones or mechanical properties of muscles (Rome et al. 1992;
522 Prestwich 1994; Navas and Bevier 2001). Furthermore as a consequence, acoustical
523 features of emitted signals at higher temperature become shorter in duration and higher in
524 rate (e.g., Schneider and Eichelberg 1974; Crespo et al. 1989; Prestwich 1994). Such
525 acoustical features are often preferably selected by females in many species (e.g., Gerhardt
526 and Huber 2002), and also in *Hyla arborea* and *H. meridionalis* (Gerhardt and Schneider
527 1980; Schneider 1982). Thus, the effect of temperature on anuran activity has been
528 proposed to explain the phenological differences in the onset of breeding season across a
529 latitude gradient, as a reflection of the successive rise of temperature from southernmost to
530 northernmost sites (Schneider 1971).

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531 However, regression analysis revealed that the major exogenous determinant of the
532 daily occurrence of lekking behavior in all populations was the estimated number of males
533 attending the lek the previous night (positive association), which showed a greater
534 predictive ability than a combination of variables measuring the weather conditions before
535 lek attendance. When the size of the group display is restricted or nil the previous night,
536 the probability of chorus formation decreases. This was probably due to a twofold reason.
537 First, *chorus size* the previous night may increase the probability of chorus formation
538 because: 1) chorusing activity may induce other males to migrate and aggregate to the

1 539 chorus in the consecutive nights (e.g., Brooke et al. 2000; Gerhardt and Huber 2002), and
2 540 it may expect that the bigger the chorus size, the further the communication distance and
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4 541 the social facilitation between conspecifics; 2) levels of circulating sexual hormones
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7 542 related to the triggering of calling behavior may remain high in males during a few days
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10 543 (for review, see Walkowiak 2007; Fritzsche et al. 1988), enabling a male to be active for
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12 544 more than a night, and hence, the larger the chorus size, the larger the number of males
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14 545 with hormonal conditions to attend chorus in subsequent days; 3) factors constraining
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17 546 chorus attendance (e.g., Murphy 1994) are expected to have a more restricted effect, in
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19 547 absolute terms, on larger chorus than in small ones, so that the larger the chorus size the
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22 548 previous night, the smaller the number of males affected by mortality, depletion of energy
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24 549 reserves or mating success that abandon the chorus in next nights. Second, the timing of
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27 550 lek formation followed a clumped pattern across the season. Once it began, chorusing
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29 551 activity occurred almost daily within the breeding season, with a mean of only 10% of the
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32 552 days lacking of choruses. Thus, it is not surprising that *chorus size* the previous night
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34 553 showed a markedly association with the daily occurrence of tree frog chorus. This
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37 554 explanatory variable functions as a first order autoregressive factor in the time series of
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39 555 *chorus occurrence* (Chatfield 2003).

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41 556 It should be noted that in this study we investigate the responses of the lek or chorus
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44 557 (i.e., males aggregation) as a whole, instead of individual responses of the males within
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46 558 the lek or chorus that cannot be discriminated by using automated recording systems.
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49 559 Chorus tenure (i.e., number of nights males attended a chorus along the season) seems to
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51 560 be abbreviated in hylids (e.g., Grafe and Meuche 2005), which may be determined by
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54 561 multiple factors, such as energetic constraints, mortality, hormonal levels fluctuations, etc.
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56 562 (Murphy 1994; Emerson 2001). However, as shown in this and other studies (Grafe and
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58 563 Meuche 2005), chorusing activity of tree frogs occurs nearly all nights within the breeding
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1 564 season, owing to an asynchronous presence of males in the chorus. Therefore, factors
2 565 constraining chorus attendance in a given male individual only can be partly accounted for
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4 566 results from acoustic monitoring as those reported here.
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9 568 Determinants of *chorus duration*
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12 569 Similarly to what was observed for timing, the nightly duration of chorusing activity
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14 570 (*chorus duration*) was influenced by a large set of exogenous factors, although with lower
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16 571 magnitude effects ($\beta < 1$). As major predictor variables of *chorus duration*, AIC
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18 572 multimodel inference selected *chorus size*, number of day, and air temperature and relative
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20 573 humidity at the onset of the chorus. The negative relationship between number of day and
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22 574 the nightly duration of tree frog chorus consistently found in all populations, except the
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24 575 population with the shortest breeding season (*CHmo*), indicates that chorusing activity
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26 576 was more intense in early season. At this time, the peak activity tends to take place
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28 577 (Brooke et al. 2000; Grafe and Meuche 2005), with longer and larger choruses. This was
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30 578 supported by our results, which showed that also the estimated number of males in the
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32 579 chorus (*chorus size*) was positively associated with the number of hours of chorusing
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34 580 (*chorus duration*). The larger the size of the chorus, the longer it lasted nightly. Previous
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36 581 studies have found such correlation in other hylids (Wells and Taigen 1986; Murphy
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38 582 1999), which may probably be owing to a twofold reason.
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47 583 First, the probability of late female arrival to the chorus is environment-dependent, as
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49 584 has been shown in *Hyla gratiosa* (Murphy 1999), and presumably increases in larger
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51 585 choruses because the number of males and females attending leks or choruses is often
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53 586 largely correlated (e.g., Henzi et al. 1995; Höglund and Alatalo 1995). Thus, it might be
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55 587 expected that males use exogenous variables in decision making related to the time
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2 588 invested in chorusing, and they prolong their calling activity in larger choruses to increase
3 589 the probability of encountering late-arriving females.

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5 590 Second, the positive association between *chorus size* and *chorus duration* may be
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7 591 interpreted as a feedback process caused by intrasexual competition and acoustic social
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9 592 facilitation. It has been well established that social facilitation markedly influences on
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11 593 acoustic displays. Playback experiments that have explored acoustic male-male interaction
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13 594 (e.g., Alexander 1961; Lopez et al. 1988; Weary et al. 1991; Jehle and Arak 1998; Bosch
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15 595 and Márquez 2001), as well as physiological studies on the neural basis of vocal
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17 596 production (for review, see Gerhardt and Huber 2002; Walkowiak 2007), have
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19 597 emphasized that acoustic displays results from a complex integration of auditory and
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21 598 motor systems. Calling behavior can be acoustically stimulated by the presence of
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23 599 conspecific calls, which may promote hormonal secretion related to sexual displays
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25 600 (Wilczynski and Chu 2001), and evoke vocal responses from both active and silent males
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27 601 (Capranica 1966; Ryan and Rand 1998). Thus, calling activity from conspecifics affects
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29 602 the timing of group acoustic displays (Brooke et al. 2000; Wells and Taigen 1986).
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31 603 Thereby, it is reasonable to assume that, in a feedback process, the number of calling
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33 604 males in a chorus influences in turn the time invested by these males in calling activity or
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35 605 even the recruitment of more males into the chorus. Sexual competition has been
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37 606 suggested as ultimate cause of this type of social facilitation (e.g., Gerhardt and Huber
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39 607 2002).

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50 609 Intraspecific variation at thermal extremes

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54 610 The contrast of determinants of timing and duration of sexual displays under different
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56 611 climatic conditions indicates that the factors constraining lekking behavior show both a
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58 612 general pattern within-species (for the timing) and a population-specific pattern (for the
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613 duration). This suggests that the exogenous determinants of the daily occurrence of tree
614 frog chorus may be stable across species ranges, despite large differences on climatic
615 conditions and altitude among their thermal extremes. However, intraspecific variation in
616 factors influencing lekking behavior may also be found, such as in chorus duration,
617 similarly to the intraspecific variation in other aspects of mating systems (territoriality or
618 display patterns; e.g., Lott 1991; Höglund and Alatalo 1995). Under different selection
619 pressures, e.g., those undergone by populations in divergent climatic conditions, it is
620 expected that different behavioral strategies evolve to achieve optimal mating results. The
621 finding of intraspecific variation in exogenous determinants of lekking behavior implies
622 the occurrence of mechanisms providing lekking species with means to cope with
623 environmental heterogeneity and changing environments. Since Iberian tree frogs show
624 both low intraspecific and interspecific genetic variation (Rosa and Oliveira 1994; Stöck
625 et al. 2008), plasticity mechanisms might presumably underlie this intraspecific variation
626 in exogenous determinants of chorus duration.

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627 Previous works based on regression analyses of multiple weather variables have found
628 that *Pseudacris crucifer* show similar environmental determinants of chorusing activity
629 between distant populations, namely those located at New Brunswick (Canada; Oseen and
630 Wassersug 2002) and North Carolina (USA; Steelman and Dorcas 2010). Moreover, major
631 predictors of chorus occurrence in this study were also consistent with those found for a
632 Central European population of *Hyla arborea* (Schneider 1971). Although more work
633 should be done, these results suggest that the species-specific factors influencing the
634 timing of group acoustic displays might be nearly homogeneous throughout the range
635 distribution of anuran species. However, few studies have examined determinants of
636 chorus duration under contrasted environmental conditions. Differences in methods used
637 between studies prevent us to draw conclusions for other species, e.g. *Lithobates*

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638 *catesbeiana*, monitored in Texas (USA, Blair 1961) and New Brunswick (Canada; Oseen
639 and Wassersug 2002). Furthermore, Navas (1996) found neither intraspecific difference in
640 body temperature of calling anurans nor in daily pattern of sexual displays between
641 populations at 2900 and 3500 m.a.s.l. of three tropical Andean species. Ritke et al. (1992)
642 and Brooke et al. (2000) examined the relationships between weather and chorusing
643 behavior at several breeding sites located at less than two kilometers from each other.
644 They found slight variations on daily and seasonal pattern of chorusing among sites due to
645 site-specific factors (e.g., water availability) as well as common factors (temperature,
646 rainfall, etc.).

647 Steelman and Dorcas (2010) proposed the use of predictive models of chorusing
648 activity based on environmental variables in calling surveys to increase the likelihood of
649 detection and assist in the interpretation of data. To extend the application of this proposed
650 method one must assume first that species-specific predictive models obtained from a
651 single location are extrapolated to other populations of the same species but under
652 different climatic conditions. Our results suggest that such extrapolation is possible. At
653 least for *Hyla molleri* and *H. meridionalis*, but probably for other species displaying in
654 leks or choruses, one model for each species may be enough to predict accurately the daily
655 or seasonal pattern of acoustic displays of populations across their distribution range.
656 However, further studies should confirm this suggestion.

657 The comparison between sympatric populations showed that both *Hyla molleri* and *H.*
658 *meridionalis* responded to the same exogenous factors determining *chorus occurrence*.
659 This similarity in behavioral responses found between species might be due to low
660 interspecific genetic variation. Although they show a clear genetic differentiation in Iberia
661 (Rosa and Oliveira 1994; Stöck et al. 2008), pre-zygotic isolation mechanisms
662 exceptionally fail between these species and hybrids have been reported from Iberian

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663 sympatric populations (Oliveira et al. 1991; Rosa and Oliveira 1994; Barbadillo and
664 Lapena 2003). Therefore, one may hypothesize that genetic divergence is still low.
665 Consequently, it is not surprising that the ecological constraints influencing the initiation
666 and maintenance of lekking behavior be very similar in Iberian tree frogs, and thus the
667 probability of occurrence of group acoustic displays be affected by the same exogenous
668 factors.

669 The results of this intraspecific comparison between populations at thermal extremes
670 might be interpreted in terms of anuran adaptation to global warming. In the last decades it
671 has become pivotal for current biology assessing the influence of temperature on animal
672 communities, to better predict and comprehend the biological consequences of the recent
673 climate change (Schwenk et al. 2009). Temperature is the most pervasive factor that
674 affects amphibian physiology, behavior (e.g., Rome et al. 1992; Wells 2007), and that
675 influences multiple stages of anuran acoustic communication, such as calling behavior,
676 acoustic signal features, signal reception, and post-reception behavior (Fritzsche et al.
677 1988; Ryan 2001; Gerhardt and Huber 2002; Narins et al. 2007). Anuran populations from
678 the southern limit of the temperate zone are particularly vulnerable to climate change.
679 Global and regional scenarios for the Mediterranean Basin suggest that this region might
680 be one of most climatically altered in next decades (Solomon et al. 2007; Giorgi and
681 Lionello 2008). For the Iberian Peninsula, climate projections for 2041–2100 predict a
682 sharp warming and pronounced decrease in rainfall, mainly in spring and summer (Trigo
683 and Palutikof 2001; Paredes et al. 2006; Solomon et al. 2007). In light of our results,
684 chorusing in European and Iberian tree frogs may not be greatly affected by the recent
685 global warming, other than to show an earlier phenology. As result of the global rise of
686 temperatures, the lower calling threshold will probably be met at an earlier date, and
687 consequently chorusing activity and breeding would also start earlier in these species. A

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688 general trend toward early breeding as an effect of global warming has been already
689 determined on amphibian populations (e.g., Beebee 1995; Blaustein et al. 2001;
690 Tryjanowski et al. 2003). However, further studies and long term acoustic monitoring will
691 be necessary to clarify the impact of these changes on population dynamics of temperate
692 zone anurans.

693

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712 **Ethical standards**

713 All experiments reported in this article comply with the current laws of Spain and
714 Portugal, the countries in which they were performed.

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716 **Conflict of interest**

717 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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719 **References**

720 Acevedo MA, Villanueva-Rivera LJ (2006) Using automated digital recording systems as effective tools for
721 the monitoring of birds and amphibians. *Wildlife Soc B* 34:211–214

722 AEMET (2008) Resumen anual climatológico 2007. Agencia Estatal de Meteorología. Ministerio de Medio
723 Ambiente y Medio Rural y Marino, Madrid

724 Alexander RD (1961) Aggressiveness, territoriality, and sexual behavior in field crickets (Orthoptera:
725 Gryllidae). *Behaviour* 17:130–223

726 Baines D (1996) Seasonal variation in lek attendance and lekking behaviour by male Black Grouse *Tetrao*
727 *tetrix*. *Ibis* 138:177–180

728 Barbadillo LJ, Lapena M (2003) Hibridación natural de *Hyla arborea* (Linnaeus, 1758) e *Hyla meridionalis*
729 (Boettger, 1874) en la Península Ibérica. *Munibe* 16:140–145

730 Beebee TJC (1995) Amphibian breeding and climate. *Nature* 374:219–220

731 Berg KS, Brumfield RT, Apanius V (2006) Phylogenetic and ecological determinants of the neotropical
732 dawn chorus. *Proc R Soc Lond B* 273:999–1005

733 Blair WF (1961) Calling and spawning seasons in a mixed population of anurans. *Ecology* 42:99–110

734 Blankenhorn HJ (1972) Meteorological variables affecting onset and duration of calling in *Hyla arborea* L.
735 and *Bufo calamita calamita* Laur. *Oecologia* 9:223–234

736 Blaustein AR, Belden LK, Olson DH, Green DM, Root TL, Kiesecker JM (2001) Amphibian breeding and
737 climate change. *Conserv Biol* 15:1804–1809

738 Bosch J, Márquez R (2001) Call timing in male-male acoustical interactions and female choice in the
739 midwife toad *Alytes obstetricans*. *Copeia* 2001:169–177

740 Bradbury JW (1981) The evolution of leks. In: Alexander RD, Tinkle DW (eds) *Natural selection and social*
741 *behavior*. Chiron Press, New York, pp 138–169

742 Bridges AS, Dorcas ME (2000) Temporal variation in anuran calling behavior: Implications for surveys and
743 monitoring programs. *Copeia* 2000:587–592

- 744 Brooke PN, Alford RA, Schwarzkopf L (2000) Environmental and social factors influence chorusing
1 745 behaviour in a tropical frog: examining various temporal and spatial scales. *Behav Ecol Sociobiol*
2 746 49:79–87
3
4 747 Broquet T, Jaquiéry J, Perrin N (2009) Opportunity for sexual selection and effective population size in the
5 748 lek-breeding European treefrog (*Hyla arborea*). *Evolution* 63:674–683
6
7 749 Burnham KP, Anderson DR (2002) Model selection and multimodel inference: a practical information-
8 750 theoretic approach, 2nd edn. Springer-Verlag, New York
9
10 751 Burnham KP, Anderson DR (2004) Multimodel inference. Understanding AIC and BIC in model selection.
11 752 *Sociol Meth Res* 33:261–304
12
13 753 Cambron ME, Bowker RG (2006) An automated digital sound recording system: the Amphibulator.
14 754 Proceeding of the Eighth IEEE International Symposium on Multimedia, San Diego, pp 592–600
15
16 755 Capranica RR (1966) Vocal response of the bullfrog to natural and synthetic mating calls. *J Acoust Soc Am*
17 756 40:1131–1139
18
19 757 Castellano S, Zanollo V, Marconi V, Berto G (2009) The mechanisms of sexual selection in a lek-breeding
20 758 anuran, *Hyla intermedia*. *Anim Behav* 77:213–224
21
22 759 Chatfield C (2003) The analysis of time series: an introduction, 6th edn. Chapman & Hall/CRC, London
23
24 760 Clutton-Brock TH, Deutsch JC, Nefdt RJC (1993) The evolution of ungulate leks. *Anim Behav* 46:1121–
25 761 1138
26
27 762 Cramer JS (1999) Predictive performance of the binary logit model in unbalanced samples. *J R Stat Soc*
28 763 48:85–9
29
30 764 Cree A (1989) Relationship between environmental conditions and nocturnal activity of the terrestrial frog,
31 765 *Leiopelma archeyi*. *J Herpetol* 23:61–68
32
33 766 Crespo EG, Oliveira ME, Rosa HD, Paillette M (1989) Mating calls of the Iberian midwife toads *Alytes*
34 767 *obstetricans boscai* and *Alytes cisternasii*. *Bioacoustics* 2:1–9
35
36 768 Dorcas ME, Price SJ, Walls SC, Barichivich WJ (2009) Auditory monitoring of anuran populations. In:
37 769 Dodd CK (ed) *Amphibian ecology and conservation. A handbook of techniques*. Oxford University
38 770 Press, Oxford, pp 281–298
39
40 771 Downes JA (1969) The swarming and mating flight of Diptera. *Annu Rev Entomol* 14:271–298
41
42 772 Emerson SB (2001) Male advertisement calls: behavioural variation and physiological processes. In: Ryan
43 773 MJ (ed) *Anuran communication*. Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, pp 36–44
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
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- 1 774 Fielding AH, Bell JF (1997) A review of methods for the assessment of prediction errors in conservation
2 775 presence/absence models. *Environ Conserv* 24:38–49
- 3 776 FitzGerald GJ, Bider JR (1974) Seasonal activity of the toad *Bufo americanus* in southern Quebec as
4 777 revealed by a sand-transect technique. *Can J Zool* 52:1–5
- 5 778 Friedl TWP, Klump GM (2005) Sexual selection in the lek-breeding European treefrog: body size, chorus
6 779 attendance, random mating and good genes. *Anim Behav* 70:1141–1154
- 7 780 Fritzsche B, Ryan MJ, Wilczynski W, Hetherington TE, Walkowiak W (1988) The evolution of the
8 781 amphibian auditory system. Wiley, New York
- 9 782 Frommolt KH, Bardeli R, Clausen M (2008) Computational bioacoustics for assessing biodiversity. BfN-
10 783 Skripten, vol. 234, Bonn
- 11 784 Fukuyama K, Kusano T (1992) Factors affecting breeding activity in a stream-breeding frog, *Buergeria*
12 785 *buergeri*. *J Herpetol* 26:88–91
- 13 786 García-París M, Montori A, Herrero P (2004) Fauna Ibérica, Vol. 24. Amphibia, Lissamphibia. Museo
14 787 Nacional de Ciencias Naturales-CSIC, Madrid
- 15 788 Gelman A (2005) Analysis of variance? Why it is more important than ever. *Ann Stat* 33:1–53
- 16 789 Gerhardt HC, Huber F (2002) Acoustic communication in insects and anurans. The University of Chicago
17 790 Press, Chicago
- 18 791 Gerhardt HC, Schneider H (1980) Mating call discrimination by females of the treefrog *Hyla meridionalis*
19 792 on Tenerife. *Behav Process* 5:143–149
- 20 793 Giorgi F, Lionello P (2008) Climate change projections for the Mediterranean region. *Global Planet Change*
21 794 63:90–104
- 22 795 Grafe TU (1997) Costs and benefits of mate choice in the lek-breeding reed frog, *Hyperolius marmoratus*.
23 796 *Anim Behav* 53:1103–1117
- 24 797 Grafe TU, Meuche I (2005) Chorus tenure and estimates of population size of male European tree frogs
25 798 *Hyla arborea*: implications for conservation. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 26:437–444
- 26 799 Grafe TU, Thein J (2001) Energetics of calling and metabolic substrate use during prolonged exercise in the
27 800 European treefrog *Hyla arborea*. *J Comp Physiol B* 171:69–76
- 28 801 Grant RA, Chadwick EA, Halliday T (2009) The lunar cycle: a cue for amphibian reproductive phenology?
29 802 *Anim Behav* 78:349–357

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56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 803 Han EN, Gatehouse AG (1991) Effect of temperature and photoperiod on the calling behaviour of a
804 migratory insect, the oriental armyworm *Mythimna separata*. *Physiol Entomol* 16:419–427
- 805 Hatano FH, Rocha CFD, Sluys MV (2002) Environmental factors affecting calling activity of a tropical
806 diurnal frog (*Hylodes phyllodes*: Leptodactylidae). *J Herpetol* 36:314–318
- 807 Heinzmann U (1970) Untersuchungen zur bio-akustik und ökologie der geburtshelferkröte, *Alytes o.*
808 *obstertricians* (Laur.). *Oecologia* 5:19–55
- 809 Henzi SP, Dyson ML, Piper SE, Passmore NE, Bishop P (1995) Chorus attendance by male and female
810 painted reed frogs (*Hyperolius marmoratus*): Environmental factors and selection pressures. *Funct Ecol*
811 9:485–491
- 812 Hijmans RJ, Cameron SE, Parra JL, Jones PG, Jarvis A (2005) Very high resolution interpolated climate
813 surfaces for global land areas. *Int J Climatol* 25:1965–1978
- 814 Höglund J, Alatalo RV (1995) *Leks*. Princeton University Press, Princeton
- 815 Hosmer DW, Lemeshow S (1989) *Applied Logistic Regression*. Wiley, New York
- 816 Jaquière J, Broquet T, Aguilar C, Evanno G, Perrin N (2009) Good genes drive female choice for mating
817 partners in the lek-breeding European treefrog. *Evolution* 64:108–115
- 818 Jehle R, Arak A (1998) Graded call variation in male Asian cricket frogs (*Rana nicobariensis*). *Bioacoustics*
819 9:35–48
- 820 Johnson JB, Omland KS (2004) Model selection in ecology and evolution. *Trends Ecol Evol* 19:101–108
- 821 Knopp T, Heimovirta M, Kokko H, Merilä J (2008) Do male moor frogs (*Rana arvalis*) lek with kin? *Mol*
822 *Ecol* 17:2522–2530
- 823 Kokko H, Sutherland WJ, Lindström J, Reynolds JD, Mackenzie A (1998) Individual mating success, lek
824 stability, and the neglected limitations of statistical power. *Anim Behav* 56:755–762
- 825 Lloyd L (1867) *The game birds and wild fowl of Sweden and Norway*. Frederick Warne, London
- 826 Llusia D, Márquez R, Bowker RG (2011) Terrestrial sound monitoring systems, a methodology for
827 quantitative calibration. *Bioacoustics* 20:277–286
- 828 Lopez PT, Narins PM, Lewis ER, Moore SW (1988) Acoustically induced call modification in the white-
829 lipped frog, *Leptodactylus albilabris*. *Anim Behav* 36:1295–1308
- 830 Lott DF (1991) *Intraspecific variation in the social systems of wild vertebrates*. Cambridge University Press,
831 Cambridge

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52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
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62
63
64
65
- 832 Loureiro A, Ferrand de Almeida N, Carretero MA, Paulo OS (2008) Atlas dos anfíbios e répteis de Portugal.
833 Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e da Biodiversidade, Lisboa
- 834 Mackenzie A, Reynolds JD, Brown VJ, Sutherland WJ (1995) Variation in male mating success on leks. *Am*
835 *Nat* 145:633–652
- 836 Manel S, Williams HC, Ormerod SJ (2001) Evaluating presence-absence models in ecology: the need to
837 account for prevalence. *J Appl Ecol* 38:921–931
- 838 Márquez R, Moreira C, do Amaral JPS, Pargana JM, Crespo EG (2005) Sound pressure level of
839 advertisement calls of *Hyla meridionalis* and *Hyla arborea*. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 26:391–395
- 840 Márquez R, Tejedo M (1990) Size-based mating pattern in the tree frog *Hyla arborea*. *Herpetologica*
841 46:176–182
- 842 Montgomery DC (2001) Design and analysis of experiments, 5th edn. Wiley, New York
- 843 Montgomery DC, Peck EA (1992) Introduction to Linear Regression Analysis. Wiley, New York
- 844 Moreira G, Barreto L (1997) Seasonal variation in nocturnal calling activity of a savanna anuran community
845 in central Brazil. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 18:49–57
- 846 Murphy CG (1994) Determinants of chorus tenure in barking treefrogs (*Hyla gratiosa*). *Behav Ecol*
847 *Sociobiol* 34:285–294
- 848 Murphy CG (1999) Nightly timing of chorusing by male barking treefrogs (*Hyla gratiosa*): The influence of
849 female arrival and energy. *Copeia* 1999:333–347
- 850 Murphy CG (2003) The cause of correlations between nightly numbers of male and female barking treefrogs
851 (*Hyla gratiosa*) attending choruses. *Behav Ecol* 14:274–281
- 852 Narins PM (2001) Ectothermy's last stand. In: Ryan MJ (ed) Anuran communication. Smithsonian
853 Institution Press, Washington, pp 61–70
- 854 Narins PM, Feng AS, Fay RR, Popper AN (2007) Hearing and sound communication in amphibians.
855 Springer, New York
- 856 Navas CA (1996) The effect of temperature on the vocal activity of tropical anurans: A comparison of high
857 and low-elevation species. *J Herpetol* 30:488–497
- 858 Navas CA, Bevier CR (2001) Thermal dependency of calling performance in the eurythermic frog
859 *Colostethus subpunctatus*. *Herpetologica* 57:384–395
- 860 Neter J, Kutner MH, Nachtsheim C, Wasserman W (1996) Applied linear statistical models, 3rd edn. Irwin,
861 Chicago

- 862 Obert HJ (1975) The dependence of calling activity in *Rana esculenta* Linné 1758 and *Rana ridibunda*
1 863 Pallas 1771 upon exogenous factors (Ranidae, Anura). *Oecologia* 18:317–328
2
3 864 Obrist MK, Pavan G, Sueur J, Riede K, Llusia D, Márquez R (2010) Bioacoustics approaches in biodiversity
4 inventories. *Abc Taxa* 8:68–99
5 865
6 866 Oliveira ME, Paillette M, Rosa HD, Crespo EG (1991) A natural hybrid between *Hyla arborea* and *Hyla*
7 867 *meridionalis* detected by mating calls. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 12:15–20
8
9 868 Oseen KL, Wassersug RJ (2002) Environmental factors influencing calling in sympatric anurans. *Oecologia*
10 133:616–625
11 869
12 870 Paillette M (1967) Rhythm of acoustic activity of *Hyla arborea* (Linné) and *Hyla meridionalis* Boettger
13 871 anurous amphibians. *CR Soc Biol* 161:986–992
14 872
15 873 Paredes D, Trigo RM, Garcia-Herrera R, Trigo IF (2006) Understanding precipitation changes in Iberia in
16 874 early spring: Weather typing and storm-tracking approaches. *J Hydrometeorol* 7:101–113
17 875
18 876 Peel MC, Finlayson BL, McMahon TA (2007) Updated world map of the Köppen-Geiger climate
19 877 classification. *Hydrol Earth Syst Sc* 11:1633–1644
20 878
21 879 Pemberton JM, Balmford AP (1987) Lekking in fallow deer. *J Zool* 213:762–765
22 880
23 881 Peterson CR, Dorcas ME (1994) Automated data acquisition. In: Heyer WR, Donnelly MA, McDiarmid
24 882 RW, Hayek LC, Foster MS (eds) *Measuring and monitoring biological diversity: standard methods for*
25 883 *amphibians*. Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, pp 47–57
26 884
27 885 Pleguezuelos JM, Márquez R, Lizana M (2002) *Atlas y Libro Rojo de los anfibios y reptiles de España*.
28 886 Dirección General de Conservación de la Naturaleza-Asociación Herpetológica Española, Madrid
29 887
30 888 Prestwich KN (1994) The energetics of acoustic signalling in anuran and insects. *Am Zool* 34:625–643
31 889
32 890 R Development Core Team (2012) R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation
33 891 for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. ISBN 3-900051-07-0, URL <http://www.R-project.org/>
34 892
35 893 Richards SA, Whittingham MJ, Stephens PA (2011) Model selection and model averaging in behavioural
36 894 ecology: the utility of the IT-AIC framework. *Behav Ecol Sociobiol* 65:77–89
37 895
38 896 Ritke ME, Babb JG, Ritke MK (1992) Temporal patterns of reproductive activity in the gray treefrog (*Hyla*
39 897 *chrysoscelis*). *J Herpetol* 26:107–111
40 898
41 899 Rome LC, Stevens ED, John-Alder HB (1992) The influence of temperature and thermal acclimation on
42 900 physiological function. In: Feder ME, Burggren WW (eds) *Environmental physiology of the*
43 901 *amphibians*. The University of Chicago Press, Chicago, pp 183–205
44 902
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63
64
65
- 892 Rosa HD, Oliveira ME (1994) Genetic differentiation of the Iberian tree frogs *Hyla arborea molleri* and
893 *Hyla meridionalis* (Amphibia, Anura). *J Zool Syst Evol Res* 32:117–128
- 894 Ryan MJ (2001) Anuran communication. Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, DC
- 895 Ryan MJ, Rand AS (1998) Evoked vocal response in male tungara frogs: pre-existing biases in male
896 responses? *Anim Behav* 56:1509–1516
- 897 Ryan MJ, Tuttle MD, Taft LK (1981) The costs and benefits of frog chorusing behaviour. *Behav Ecol*
898 *Sociobiol* 8:273–278
- 899 Salvador A, Carrascal LM (1990) Reproductive phenology and temporal patterns of mate access in
900 Mediterranean anurans. *J Herpetol* 24:438–441
- 901 Schneider H (1971) Die steuerung des täglichen rufbeginns beim Laubfrosch, *Hyla arborea arborea* (L.)
902 *Oecologia* 8:310–320
- 903 Schneider H (1974) Structure of the mating calls and relationships of the European tree frogs (Hylidae,
904 Anura). *Oecologia* 14:99–110
- 905 Schneider H (1982) Phonotaxis bei weibchen des kanarischen Laubfrosches, *Hyla meridionalis*. *Zool Anz*
906 208:161–174
- 907 Schneider H, Eichelberg H (1974) The mating call of hybrids of the fire-bellied toad and yellow-bellied toad
908 (*Bombina bombina* (L.), *Bombina v. variegata* (L.), Discoglossidae, Anura). *Oecologia* 16:61–71
- 909 Schwartz JJ, Ressel SJ, Bevier CR (1995) Carbohydrate and calling: depletion of muscle glycogen and the
910 chorusing dynamics of the neotropical treefrog *Hyla microcephala*. *Behav Ecol Sociobiol* 37:125–135
- 911 Schwenk K, Padilla DK, Bakken GS, Full RJ (2009) Grand challenges in organismal biology. *Integr Comp*
912 *Biol* 49:7–14
- 913 Shirose LJ, Bishop CA, Green DM, MacDonald CJ, Brooks RJ, Helferty NJ (1997) Validation tests of an
914 amphibian call count survey technique in Ontario, Canada. *Herpetologica* 53:312–320
- 915 Sokal RR, Rohlf FJ (1995) Biometry: the principles and practice of statistics in biological research, 3rd edn.
916 Freedman, New York
- 917 Solomon S, Qin D, Manning M, Chen Z, Marquis M, Averyt KB, Tignor M, Miller HL (2007) Climate
918 change 2007: The physical science basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment
919 Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
920 and New York

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54
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58
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60
61
62
63
64
65
- 921 Steelman CK, Dorcas ME (2010) Anuran calling survey optimization: developing and testing predictive
922 models of anuran calling activity. *J Herpetol* 44:61–68
- 923 Stöck M, Dubey S, Klütsch C, Litvinchuk SN, Scheidt U, Perrin N (2008) Mitochondrial and nuclear
924 phylogeny of circum-Mediterranean tree frogs from the *Hyla arborea* group. *Mol Phylogenet Evol*
925 49:1019–1024
- 926 Symonds MRE, Moussalli A (2011) A brief guide to model selection, multimodel inference and model
927 averaging in behavioural ecology using Akaike’s information criterion. *Behav Ecol Sociobiol* 65:13–21
- 928 Taigen TL, Wells KD (1985) Energetics of vocalization by an anuran amphibian (*Hyla versicolor*). *J Comp*
929 *Physiol B* 155:163–170
- 930 Trigo RM, Palutikof JP (2001) Precipitation scenarios over Iberia: A comparison between direct GCM
931 output and different downscaling techniques. *J Climate* 14:4422–4446
- 932 Tryjanowski P, Mariusz R, Sparks TH (2003) Changes in spawning dates of common frogs and common
933 toads in western Poland in 1978–2002. *Ann Zool Fenn* 40:459–464
- 934 Tuttle MD, Ryan MJ (1981) Bat predation and the evolution of frog vocalizations in the Neotropics. *Science*
935 214:677–678
- 936 Walkowiak W (2007) Call production and neural basis of vocalization. In: Narins PM, Feng AS, Fay RR,
937 Popper AN (eds) *Hearing and sound communication in amphibians*. Springer, New York, pp 87–112
- 938 Weary DM, Lambrechts MM, Krebs JR (1991) Does singing exhaust male great tits? *Anim Behav* 41:540–
939 542
- 940 Weir LA, Mossman MJ (2005) North American amphibian monitoring program (NAAMP). In: Lannoo M
941 (ed) *Amphibian declines: the conservation status of United States species*. University of California
942 Press, Berkeley, pp 307–13
- 943 Wells KD (1977) The social behaviour of anuran amphibians. *Anim Behav* 25:666–693
- 944 Wells KD (2007) *The ecology and behavior of amphibians*. The University of Chicago Press, Chicago
- 945 Wells KD, Taigen TL (1986) The effect of social interactions on calling energetics in the gray treefrog (*Hyla*
946 *versicolor*). *Behav Ecol Sociobiol* 19:9–18
- 947 Widemo F, Owens IPF (1995) Lek size, male mating skew and the evolution of lekking. *Nature* 373:148–
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949 Wilczynski W, Chu J (2001) Acoustic communication, endocrine control, and the neurochemical systems of
950 the brain. In: Ryan MJ (ed) Anuran communication. Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, pp 23–
951 35
952 Zuur AF, Ieno EN, Elphick CS (2010) A protocol for data exploration to avoid common statistical problems.
953 Meth Ecol Evol 1:3–14

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2 **955 Fig. 1** Location of study sites and tree frogs ranges in Iberian Peninsula (Pleguezuelos et al. 2002;
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4 **956** Loureiro et al. 2008). Species ranges are plotted through 10x10 km UTM squares (Universal Transverse
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6 **957** Mercator coordinate system) with occurrence of *Hyla molleri* (grey open squares) and *H. meridionalis*
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8 **958** (black closed squares). *CHmo* and *HHmo*: cold and hot population of *H. molleri*, respectively. *CHme* and
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10 **959** *HHme*: cold and hot population of *H. meridionalis*, respectively. *HHmo* and *CHme* are sympatric
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12 **960** populations

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16 **962 Fig. 2** Scatter plots and logistic functions showing the univariate relationships between *chorus*
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18 **963** *occurrence* (probability of daily presence / absence of tree frog chorus) and its major exogenous
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20 **964** determinants in each study site, as shown by AIC multimode inference: (top) *prevSizeCHORUS*,
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22 **965** maximum size of the chorus the previous night (*calling index* with values between 0 and 5); (high)
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24 **966** *chgTEMP*, change in daytime mean of air temperature (°C) from the previous day; (low) *dayRH*, mean
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26 **967** relative humidity (%) during daytime; and (bottom) *chgPRESS*, change in daytime mean of barometric
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28 **968** pressure (hPa) from the previous day. *CHmo* and *HHmo*: cold and hot population of *Hyla molleri*,
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30 **969** respectively. *CHme* and *HHme*: cold and hot population of *H. meridionalis*, respectively. *HHmo* and
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32 **970** *CHme* are sympatric populations. Size of points is proportional to the square root of the number of
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34 **971** observations

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38 **973 Fig. 3** Scatter plots and linear functions showing the univariate relationships between *chorus duration*
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40 **974** (nightly duration of tree frog chorus) and its major exogenous determinants in each study site, as shown
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42 **975** by AIC multimode inference: (top) *sizeCHORUS*, maximum size of the chorus that night (*calling index*
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44 **976** with values between 0 and 5); (high) *numDAY*, day number of the breeding season (from 1 onwards);
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46 **977** (low) *onsetAirTEMP*, air temperature (°C) at the onset of the chorus; and (bottom) *onsetRH*, relative
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48 **978** humidity (%) at the onset of the chorus. *CHmo* and *HHmo*: cold and hot population of *Hyla molleri*,
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50 **979** respectively. *CHme* and *HHme*: cold and hot population of *H. meridionalis*, respectively. *HHmo* and
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52 **980** *CHme* are sympatric populations. Size of points is proportional to the square root of the number of
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54 **981** observations

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2 984 **Table 1** General features of habitat, thermal regime and weather conditions in the study sites

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6 986 **Table 2** General features of chorusing activity of tree frogs in the study sites^a

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10 988 **Table 3** Social and environmental variables examined by multiple binomial regression as potential
11 989 factors influencing the daily occurrence of tree frog chorus at the breeding points (*chorus occurrence*)

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16 991 **Table 4** Social and environmental variables examined by multiple linear regression as potential factors
17 992 influencing the nightly duration of tree frog chorus (*chorus duration*)

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22 994 **Table 5** Standardized regression coefficients (β) and relative importance (Σw_i) from multiple binomial
23 995 regressions of the daily occurrence of tree frog chorus (*chorus occurrence*) on 17 social and
24 996 environmental variables (Table 3), for four sites located at the Iberian thermal extremes of the tree frogs
25 997 range

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30 999 **Table 6** Standardized regression coefficients (β) and relative importance (Σw_i) from multiple linear
31 1000 regressions of the nightly duration of tree frog chorus (*chorus duration*) on 16 social and environmental
32 1001 variables (Table 4), for four sites located at the Iberian thermal extremes of the tree frogs range

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36 1003 **Appendix 1** Binomial regression models selected by AIC multimodel inference ($\Delta AICc < 2$) for the
37 1004 daily occurrence of tree frog chorus (*chorus occurrence*) located at the Iberian thermal extremes of their
38 1005 distribution range

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42 1007 **Appendix 2** Linear regression models selected by AIC multimodel inference ($\Delta AICc < 2$) for the nightly
43 1008 duration of tree frog chorus (*chorus duration*) located at the Iberian thermal extremes of their distribution
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Figure 3

Table 1 General features of habitat, thermal regime and weather conditions in the study sites

		<i>Hyla molleri</i>		<i>Hyla meridionalis</i>	
		Cold	Hot	Cold	Hot
Habitat	Latitude	43° 02' 41"	39° 22' 46"	39° 22' 46"	36° 59' 30"
	Longitude	6° 08' 14"	7° 28' 31"	7° 28' 31"	6° 26' 33"
	Altitude (m.a.s.l.)	1490	408	408	3
	Area (m ²)	450	3286	3286	16160
	Breeding site	temporary	permanent	permanent	temporary
Thermal regime ^a	Annual mean temperature (°C)	7.61	15.40	15.40	17.88
	Mean temperature of wettest Q (°C)	4.3	9.2	9.2	14.3
	Level of themal extremity (%) ^b	98.57	77.57	73.09	96.93
Weather conditions ^c		Mean ± SD (Range)	Mean ± SD (Range)	Mean ± SD (Range)	Mean ± SD (Range)
	Air temperature (°C)	9.2 ± 6.3 (-1.5–27.5)	15.0 ± 7.2 (-0.4–38.7)	13.0 ± 5.8 (-0.4–31.2)	15.6 ± 5.8 (-0.6–33.1)
	Water temperature (°C)	13.0 ± 3.1 (6.2–24.9)	19.2 ± 4.6 (8.9–30.1)	17.7 ± 4.2 (8.9–26.0)	19.2 ± 3.7 (11.5–31.2)
	Relative humidity (%)	94.5 ± 12.9 (32.9–104.1)	61.9 ± 20.4 (16.7–96.8)	66.0 ± 18.4 (27.1–96.8)	73.6 ± 18.1 (19.4–97.2)
	Barometric pressure (hPa)	976.8 ± 5.1 (962.5–987.8)	950.5 ± 5.9 (935.1–1010.7)	950.0 ± 5.6 (935.1–1010.7)	1018.5 ± 6.2 (1005.4–1037.1)
	Cloud cover (okta)	5.6 ± 2.5 (0–9)	3.7 ± 3.0 (0–9)	4.3 ± 2.9 (0–9)	2.7 ± 3.0 (0–9)

^a Data obtained from interpolated climate surfaces (Hijmans et al. 2005). Q: quarter of the calendar year.

^b Percentage of UTM 10x10 km squares in the species range (Pleguezuelos et al. 2002; Loureiro et al. 2008) with an annual mean temperature below (in the case of hot extremes) or above (in the case of cold extremes) the annual mean temperature of the study site (Hijmans et al. 2005).

^c Data obtained during study period from data loggers and automatic weather stations of the National Meteorological Services (AEMET, Spain; IP, Portugal).

Table 2 General features of chorusing activity of tree frogs in the study sites^a

		<i>Hyla molleri</i>		<i>Hyla meridionalis</i>	
		Cold	Hot	Cold	Hot
<i>Chorus occurrence</i>	Onset	8-May-2007	12-Feb-2007	12-Feb-2007	26-Dec-2006
	End	25-Jun-2007	5-Jul-2007	3-Jun-2007	21-May-2007
	Season duration (days)	48	144	111	146
	N° days (%) with chorus	38 (79.2)	84 (58.3)	56 (50.5)	118 (80.8)
	N° days (%) without chorus	10 (20.8)	7 (4.9)	5 (4.5)	13 (8.9)
	N° days (%) without data	0 (0.0)	53 (36.8)	50 (45.0)	15 (10.3)
<i>Chorus duration</i> ^b	Mean ± SD (CV)	3.6 ± 2.1 (0.58)	5.6 ± 1.9 (0.34)	5.1 ± 2.5 (0.49)	7.2 ± 3.2 (0.44)
	Range	1–9	1–10	1–10	1–13
	N° tracks with chorus	138	469	284	855
	% tracks with chorus between sunset and sunrise	89.9	99.1	97.1	98.7
<i>Chorus size</i> ^c	Mean ± SD (CV)	4.5 ± 1.0 (0.21)	4.4 ± 0.8 (0.17)	4.5 ± 0.7 (0.16)	4.6 ± 0.8 (0.18)
	% of days with maximum chorus size (value = 5)	76.3	61.9	60.7	73.1

^a Data obtained by automatic recording systems (ARS), with a schedule of 3 minutes per hour, 24 hours per day.

^b Number of hours per night of chorusing activity. Each track corresponded to a different hour of the day.

^c Daily maximum value of a *calling index* (0–5) that was estimated following a modified version of NAAMP protocol (Weir and Mossman 2005). Maximum value: 5 = full chorus, calls are constant, continuous, and overlapping. Percentage is calculated from the number of days with chorus.

Table 3 Social and environmental variables examined by multiple binomial regression as potential factors influencing the daily occurrence of tree frog chorus at the breeding points (*chorus occurrence*)

Label	Variable
prevSizeCHORUS	Maximum size of the chorus the previous night (<i>calling index</i> with values between 0 and 5)
numDAY	Day number of the study season (from 1 onwards)
minDayTEMP	Minimum air temperature (°C) during daytime
maxDayTEMP	Maximum air temperature (°C) during daytime
chgTEMP	Change in daytime mean of air temperature (°C) from the previous day
2hSunsTEMP	Air temperature (°C) two hours before sunset
dayRH	Mean relative humidity (%) during daytime
prevRH	Mean relative humidity (%) during daytime the previous day
twoRH	Mean relative humidity (%) during daytime two days previously
2hSunsRH	Relative humidity (%) two hours before sunset
dayPRESS	Mean barometric pressure (hPa) during daytime
chgPRESS	Change in daytime mean of barometric pressure (hPa) from the previous day
2hSunsCLOUD	Cloud cover (okta) two hours before sunset
phaseMOON	Daily percentage of moon illumination, from 0% (new moon) to 100% (full moon)
minDayTEMP ²	Quadratic term of minDayTEMP
maxDayTEMP ²	Quadratic term of maxDayTEMP
2hSunsTEMP ²	Quadratic term of 2hSunsTEMP

The daytime was taken as time from sunrise to two hours before sunset, when no chorus typically occurs in the study sites and it is expected that the decision making related to migration to the breeding points and chorus attendance takes place.

Table 4 Social and environmental variables examined by multiple linear regression as potential factors influencing the nightly duration of tree frog chorus (*chorus duration*)

Label	Variable
prevCHORUS	Chorus duration the previous night (number of hours)
sizeCHORUS	Maximum size of the chorus that night (<i>calling index</i> with values between 0 and 5)
numDAY	Day number of the breeding season (from 1 onwards)
meanAirTEMP	Mean air temperature (°C) during the chorus
onsetAirTEMP	Air temperature (°C) at the onset of the chorus
meanWatTEMP	Mean water temperature (°C) during the chorus
onsetWatTEMP	Water temperature (°C) at the onset of the chorus
nightRH	Mean relative humidity (%) during the chorus
onsetRH	Relative humidity (%) at the onset of the chorus
nightPRESS	Mean barometric pressure (hPa) during the chorus
nightCLOUD	Mean cloud cover (okta) during the chorus
phaseMOON	Daily percentage of moon illumination, from 0% (new moon) to 100% (full moon)
meanAirTEMP ²	Quadratic term of meanAirTEMP
onsetAirTEMP ²	Quadratic term of onsetAirTEMP
meanWatTEMP ²	Quadratic term of meanWatTEMP
onsetWatTEMP ²	Quadratic term of onsetWatTEMP

Table 5 Standardized regression coefficients (β) and relative importance (Σw_i) from multiple binomial regressions of the daily occurrence of tree frog chorus (*chorus occurrence*) on 17 social and environmental variables (Table 3), for four sites located at the Iberian thermal extremes of the tree frogs range

	<i>Hyla molleri</i>				<i>Hyla meridionalis</i>			
	Cold site (n = 86)		Hot site (n = 175)		Cold site (n = 117)		Hot site (n = 252)	
	β	Σw_i	β	Σw_i	β	Σw_i	β	Σw_i
prevSizeCHORUS								
level 2	0.72	-			0.51	-	0.84	-
level 3	7.07	-	2.81	-	2.07	-	1.22	-
level 4	1.16	-	2.80	-	2.34	-	2.50	-
level 5	4.75	1.00	4.56	1.00	4.54	1.00	22.54	1.00
numDAY								
minDayTEMP	0.74	0.33						
maxDayTEMP			0.83	0.35	0.97	0.30	-0.38	0.11
chgTEMP	2.12	1.00	0.40	0.10	0.51	0.11		
2hSunsTEMP								
dayRH			0.03	0.10			1.92	1.00
prevRH	1.19	0.39			-0.74	0.15		
twoRH			-0.74	0.34			-0.83	0.29
2hSunsRH								
dayPRESS			-0.84	0.24	0.61	0.22	0.73	0.34
chgPRESS	0.98	0.27	1.37	1.00	0.40	0.10	0.36	0.12
2hSunsCLOUD								
phaseMOON			-0.54	0.18				
minDayTEMP ²								
maxDayTEMP ²								
2hSunsTEMP ²								
N° of predictors	5		8		6		6	
Nagelkerke's R ²	0.672		0.763		0.723		0.890	
Explained Deviance	0.507		0.612		0.564		0.794	
Maximum VIF	2.1		2.9		2.7		2.3	

Model selection was based on multimodel inference, using Akaike information criterion corrected for small sample sizes (full set of models, $\Delta AIC_c < 2$) and parameters estimated by model averaging. Variance inflation factor (VIF) was set < 3 as multicollinearity threshold. Σw_i : relative importance of each variable in the AIC multimodel inference, calculated as sum of Akaike weights of the models where each variable was selected (Appendix 1).

Table 6 Standardized regression coefficients (β) and relative importance (Σw_i) from multiple linear regressions of the nightly duration of tree frog chorus (*chorus duration*) on 16 social and environmental variables (Table 4), for four sites located at the Iberian thermal extremes of the tree frogs range

	<i>Hyla molleri</i>				<i>Hyla meridionalis</i>			
	Cold site (n = 38)		Hot site (n = 84)		Cold site (n = 56)		Hot site (n = 118)	
	β	Σw_i	β	Σw_i	β	Σw_i	β	Σw_i
prevCHORUS	0.21	0.42			-0.18	0.37	0.16	1.00
sizeCHORUS								
level 3							0.01	-
level 4			0.10	-	0.22	-	0.46	-
level 5			0.30	0.84	0.55	1.00	0.80	1.00
numDAY	0.18	0.05	-0.63	1.00	-0.48	1.00	-0.35	1.00
meanAirTEMP								
onsetAirTEMP	0.78	1.00	0.46	1.00	0.16	0.27	0.22	1.00
meanWatTEMP	-0.33	0.71						
onsetWatTEMP								
nightRH								
onsetRH	0.17	0.31	0.49	1.00	0.21	0.60	0.25	1.00
nightPRESS			0.14	0.38			-0.06	0.29
nightCLOUD			-0.11	0.21	0.17	0.37	0.14	1.00
phaseMOON	0.27	0.61						
meanAirTEMP ²								
onsetAirTEMP ²								
meanWatTEMP ²								
onsetWatTEMP ²								
N° of predictors	6		6		6		7	
Model Adjust-R ²	0.376		0.465		0.520		0.685	
Maximum VIF	2.6		2.4		2.6		2.9	

Model selection was based on multimodel inference, using Akaike information criterion corrected for small sample sizes (full set of models, $\Delta AIC_c < 2$) and parameters estimated by model averaging. Variance inflation factor (VIF) was set < 3 as multicollinearity threshold. Σw_i : relative importance of each variable in the AIC multimodel inference, calculated as sum of Akaike weights of the models where each variable was selected (Appendix 2).

Appendix 1 Binomial regression models selected by AIC multimodel inference ($\Delta\text{AICc} < 2$) for the daily occurrence of tree frog chorus (*chorus occurrence*) located at the Iberian thermal extremes of their distribution range

<i>Hyla molleri</i>	Cold site (n = 86 days)		df	logLik	AICc	ΔAICc	w_i
	prevSizeCHORUS + chgTEMP + prevRH		7	-30.04	75.52	0.00	0.26
prevSizeCHORUS + chgTEMP		6	-31.31	75.68	0.15	0.24	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgTEMP + chgPRESS		7	-30.50	76.43	0.90	0.17	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgTEMP + prevRH + minDayTEMP		8	-29.55	76.96	1.44	0.13	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgTEMP + minDayTEMP + chgPRESS		8	-29.73	77.33	1.81	0.11	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgTEMP + minDayTEMP		7	-31.00	77.45	1.92	0.10	
	Hot site (n = 175 days)		df	logLik	AICc	ΔAICc	w_i
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + maxDayTEMP		6	-48.65	109.81	0.00	0.12	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS		5	-49.78	109.92	0.11	0.11	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + twoRH		6	-48.75	110.01	0.20	0.11	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + dayPRESS		6	-48.83	110.16	0.35	0.10	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + twoRH + dayPRESS		7	-48.08	110.82	1.02	0.07	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + maxDayTEMP + phaseMOON		7	-48.13	110.92	1.11	0.07	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + maxDayTEMP + dayPRESS		7	-48.15	110.98	1.17	0.07	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + phaseMOON		6	-49.41	111.32	1.51	0.06	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + twoRH + chgTEMP		7	-48.35	111.38	1.57	0.05	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + twoRH + phaseMOON		7	-48.37	111.42	1.61	0.05	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + maxDayTEMP + twoRH		7	-48.41	111.48	1.68	0.05	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + dayRH		6	-49.50	111.50	1.70	0.05	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + maxDayTEMP + dayRH		7	-48.49	111.64	1.83	0.05	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS + chgTEMP		6	-49.61	111.71	1.91	0.05	
<i>H. meridionalis</i>	Cold site (n = 117 days)		df	logLik	AICc	ΔAICc	w_i
prevSizeCHORUS		5	-37.02	84.59	0.00	0.24	
prevSizeCHORUS + maxDayTEMP		6	-36.11	84.98	0.40	0.19	
prevSizeCHORUS + prevRH		6	-36.38	85.52	0.93	0.15	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgTEMP		6	-36.64	86.05	1.46	0.11	
prevSizeCHORUS + maxDayTEMP + dayPRESS		7	-35.53	86.09	1.50	0.11	
prevSizeCHORUS + dayPRESS		6	-36.73	86.22	1.63	0.10	
prevSizeCHORUS + chgPRESS		6	-36.80	86.37	1.79	0.10	
	Hot site (n = 252 days)		df	logLik	AICc	ΔAICc	w_i
prevSizeCHORUS + dayHR		6	-37.55	87.44	0.00	0.29	
prevSizeCHORUS + dayHR + dayPRESS		7	-36.86	88.18	0.74	0.20	
prevSizeCHORUS + dayHR + dayPRESS + twoRH		8	-36.11	88.81	1.37	0.14	
prevSizeCHORUS + dayHR + twoRH		7	-37.19	88.85	1.41	0.14	
prevSizeCHORUS + dayHR + chgPRESS		7	-37.36	89.17	1.74	0.12	
prevSizeCHORUS + dayHR + maxDayTEMP		7	-37.43	89.32	1.88	0.11	

AICc: Akaike information criterion corrected for small sample sizes. w_i : Akaike weights. Interactions were excluded. Variable descriptions in Table 3.

Appendix 2 Linear regression models selected by AIC multimodel inference ($\Delta\text{AICc} < 2$) for the nightly duration of tree frog chorus (*chorus duration*) located at the Iberian thermal extremes of their distribution range

<i>Hyla molleri</i>	Cold site (n = 38 nights)					df	logLik	AICc	ΔAICc	w_i
	onsetAirTEMP + MeanWatTEMP + phaseMOON					5	-71.59	155.06	0.00	0.13
	onsetAirTEMP + phaseMOON					4	-73.13	155.46	0.40	0.11
	onsetAirTEMP + MeanWatTEMP + phaseMOON + prevCHORUS					6	-70.39	155.48	0.42	0.11
	onsetAirTEMP + MeanWatTEMP + prevCHORUS					5	-71.91	155.69	0.63	0.10
	onsetAirTEMP + MeanWatTEMP + phaseMOON + onsetRH					6	-70.64	156.00	0.94	0.08
	onsetAirTEMP + MeanWatTEMP					4	-73.50	156.22	1.15	0.08
	onsetAirTEMP					3	-74.93	156.57	1.51	0.06
	onsetAirTEMP + phaseMOON + onsetRH					5	-72.43	156.73	1.67	0.06
	onsetAirTEMP + MeanWatTEMP + phaseMOON + prevCHORUS + onsetRH					7	-69.53	156.79	1.73	0.06
	onsetAirTEMP + phaseMOON + prevCHORUS					5	-72.46	156.79	1.73	0.06
	onsetAirTEMP + MeanWatTEMP + prevCHORUS + onsetRH					6	-71.05	156.82	1.75	0.06
	onsetAirTEMP + MeanWatTEMP + onsetRH					5	-72.54	156.95	1.89	0.05
	onsetAirTEMP + MeanWatTEMP + prevCHORUS + numDAY					6	-71.15	157.01	1.95	0.05
	Hot site (n = 84 nights)					df	logLik	AICc	ΔAICc	w_i
	numDAY + onsetAirTEMP + onsetRH + sizeCHORUS					7	-146.04	307.55	0.00	0.41
	numDAY + onsetAirTEMP + onsetRH + sizeCHORUS + nightPRESS					8	-145.45	308.82	1.27	0.22
	numDAY + onsetAirTEMP + onsetRH + sizeCHORUS + nightCLOUD					8	-145.47	308.87	1.32	0.21
	numDAY + onsetAirTEMP + onsetRH + nightPRESS					6	-148.14	309.37	1.82	0.16
	Cold site (n = 56 nights)					df	logLik	AICc	ΔAICc	w_i
	sizeCHORUS + numDAY + onsetRH + prevCHORUS					7	-107.81	231.95	0.00	0.17
	sizeCHORUS + numDAY + onsetRH					6	-109.18	232.08	0.13	0.16
	sizeCHORUS + numDAY + nightCLOUD					6	-109.29	232.29	0.34	0.14
	sizeCHORUS + numDAY + onsetRH + onsetAirTEMP					7	-108.23	232.78	0.83	0.11
	sizeCHORUS + numDAY + nightCLOUD + prevCHORUS					7	-108.31	232.95	1.00	0.10
	sizeCHORUS + numDAY + onsetRH + prevCHORUS + onsetAirTEMP					8	-107.01	233.09	1.14	0.10
	sizeCHORUS + numDAY					5	-111.00	233.20	1.25	0.09
	sizeCHORUS + numDAY + onsetRH + nightCLOUD					7	-108.74	233.82	1.87	0.07
	sizeCHORUS + numDAY + nightCLOUD + onsetAirTEMP					7	-108.78	233.89	1.94	0.06
	Hot site (n = 118 nights)					df	logLik	AICc	ΔAICc	w_i
	sizeCHORUS + numDAY + onsetRH + prevCHORUS + nightCLOUD + onsetAirTEMP					10	-230.96	483.97	0.00	0.71
	sizeCHORUS + numDAY + onsetRH + prevCHORUS + nightCLOUD + onsetAirTEMP + nightPRESS					11	-230.62	485.73	1.76	0.29

AICc: Akaike information criterion corrected for small sample sizes. w_i : Akaike weights. Interactions were excluded. Variable descriptions in Table 4.